

Evaluation of theses on dissociation and dissociative disorders in Türkiye: A meta-synthesis study

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to evaluate the aims, results and recommendations of theses published in Türkiye on dissociation and dissociative disorders by meta-synthesis method. In our study, 144 theses published between 1995 and 2022 and containing the keywords "dissociation" and/or "dissociative disorders" in the database of the National Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education were included. These were evaluated by thematic content analysis method in terms of university, institute, science/department, type, subject, year, specialty (master's/doctorate/expertise in medicine), aim, conclusion and recommendations. It was determined that 45.8% of the theses on dissociation and dissociative disorders in Türkiye were published between 2018-2022, 55.6% were expertise in medicine theses, 53.5% were in the field of psychiatry, 97.2% were original research studies, and 96.5% employed quantitative methodology. 29.2% of the dissertations within the scope of our study examined the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in a non-clinical population, 26.4% of the dissertations found a relationship between dissociation and traumatic experiences, family dynamics, and other psychological characteristics, and 16.0% of the dissertations suggested the need for more cross-sectional and/or longitudinal research. This is the first study to evaluate thesis abstracts containing the terms dissociation and/or dissociative disorders using the meta-synthesis method. It is believed that meta-synthesis studies on dissociation will contribute to the development of short-term therapy models and raise awareness about dissociative disorders, the psychiatric diagnosis group most closely associated with traumatic experiences.

Keywords: Dissociation; dissociative disorders; meta-synthesis; thesis; trauma

INTRODUCTION

To reintegrate the functions of identity, consciousness, memory, and perception of the environment that have been fragmented by traumatic experiences, individuals strive for a more "holistic" perspective and a more "dynamic" balance regarding themselves and the world. According to Ozturk (2020a), dissociation is an extreme and intense integration effort of a divided and multiple consciousness system. Dissociation, as a dynamic and mobile process, is a strong desire for integration or unification rather than a division (Ozturk, 2020a; Ozturk et al., 2021). Reconsidered on the axis of modern psychotraumatology and dissoanalysis theories, dissociation is the transformation of the individual's singular consciousness into a multiple consciousness system process with the psychopathogenic effect of ordinary life experiences and defenses that distract from the traumatic memories that the individual's singular consciousness witnessed during or after psychosocial oppressions, traumatic events, and violence-oriented experiences (Ozturk, 2022a; 2022b; 2022c). Dissociative reactions to minimal traumas in actual life, dissociative experiences that develop in the face of violence-oriented negative child-rearing styles, and dissociative disorders that develop as a result of chronic traumatic events beginning in early childhood are actually quite daily life experiences that continue to demonstrate their adaptive and psychopathogenic effects from the past to the present in a complex manner (Ozturk, 2022a).

The first scientific studies on dissociation and dissociative disorders were conducted in the context of treating cases of "hysteria", as it was known at the time - those who now meet the diagnostic criteria for dissociative identity disorder. Jean Martin Charcot and Pierre Janet are among the prominent scientists who conducted the first and pioneering studies on the clinical dimension of dissociation. Charcot's lectures on hysteria cases with an emphasis on neurology and psychiatry piqued the scientific interest of numerous clinicians, particularly Pierre Janet. Janet, who attended Charcot's lectures and pioneered

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research on somnambulisms in cases of hysteria, is one of the most influential psychologist on dissociation and dissociative disorders (Ozturk, 2020a; Ozturk & Derin, 2020). Academic interest in dissociative disorders increased significantly between 1990 and 1995, and since the turn of the 21st century, prestigious international journals in many nations, including the United States, Türkiye, Belgium, France, Netherlands, Canada, and Japan, have published important articles in this field. In clinical psychology and psychiatry in Türkiye, the first book on dissociation and dissociative disorders was "*Trauma and Dissociation: Basic Book of Psychotraumatology*". Dissociative disorders are among the most basic psychiatric diagnostic groups characterized by self-harming behaviors, suicide attempts, interruptions of consciousness, amnesia, concentration difficulties, anger outbursts and feelings of uncertainty in identity (Putnam, 1991; Ross & Halpern, 2009).

Purpose and importance of the research

The significance of this study lies in its examination of theses on dissociation and dissociative disorders in Türkiye and its determination of how the academic subjects of "*dissociation*" and "*dissociative disorders*" are approached, for what purposes they are conducted, and what results and recommendations are reached. The aim of this meta-synthesis-based study of Turkish theses on "*dissociation*" and "*dissociative disorders*" is to determine how "*dissociation*" and "*dissociative disorders*" are studied by different disciplines, as well as which aims, results, and recommendations are included in this direction. It is expected that this meta-synthesis study, which is organized according to the years, universities/institutes, disciplines/major disciplines, methods, aims, results, and recommendations, will provide significant scientific contributions to all academicians and clinicians working on dissociation and dissociative disorders. Within the scope of the research, it was sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the distribution of theses containing the keywords "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" according to their discipline/major discipline and characteristics (original research/review)?
2. What were the topics of theses containing the keywords "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" distributed according to the methodology employed?
3. What is the distribution of the objectives of theses that include "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" as keywords according to their type (master's degree/doctorate/expertise in medicine)?
4. What is the distribution of the results of theses with the keywords "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" according to their type (master's degree/doctorate/expertise in medicine)?
5. What is the distribution of theses containing the keywords "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" by type (master's/doctoral/expertise in medicine)?

METHOD

In this study, qualitative methods were used to evaluate theses on "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" using thematic content analysis (meta-synthesis; Calık & Sozibilir, 2014). Thematic content analysis studies involve the comparative determination of similarities and differences by

analyzing the research on specific topics using a qualitative methodology. Meta-synthesis method is a technique within the field of content analysis studies, and it is the interpretation and synthesis of publications on the same topic from a critical standpoint by developing themes or main templates (Merriam, 2013). The population of the study consists of theses published in Türkiye between 1995 and 2022 with the keywords "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" in the database of the National Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education (YÖK). The sample for this study consists of 144 theses with the keywords "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" published between 1995 and 2022 in the database of the YÖK National Thesis Center.

Data collection and inclusion criteria

Employing the YÖK National Thesis Center database, we determined which theses to include in our study. The inclusion criteria for the study were a postgraduate thesis published in the YÖK National Thesis Center database, the exact inclusion of the terms "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" as keywords, and a publication date of 1995 or later. 1995 was chosen as the starting point because it is the year of the oldest thesis in the database of the YÖK National Thesis Center.

Limitations of the study

This study is limited to 144 theses published between 1995 and 2022 in the YÖK National Thesis Center database as of 23 May 2023. These theses were included in the scope of the study as a result of keyword searches for "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*". These uploaded to the database of the YÖK National Thesis Center after 23 May 2023 were excluded from the study. Although a detailed examination was not possible because 17 theses lacked publication permission, these theses were included in the study and data on the imprint (year of publication, type of thesis, abstract, etc.) of the relevant theses in the database of the YÖK National Thesis Center were analyzed. The theses in which the terms "*dissociation*" and/or "*dissociative disorders*" were not included in the keywords and were not included as written represent a further limitation of our study.

Coding process and themes

In order to eliminate possible coding errors and ensure the validity and reliability of the research, two researchers read the theses included in the study multiple times and identified their commonalities. In order to ensure the subject's integrity in the analysis and to facilitate the synthesis phase, themes were developed by taking into account these common characteristics. The suggestions of Merriam and Tisdell (2015) were considered in the development of themes:

1. Themes can be both a literary concept and an expression deemed appropriate by the researcher.
2. Developing themes is possible by drawing inferences from the data.
3. Some of the primary themes can also be presented as secondary themes.
4. The names of the themes should correspond to the focus of the work.

After identifying the themes, the coding phase was initiated. During this phase, descriptive information collected from each thesis is used to convert the data into numerical data. The required coding should be both broad enough to encompass all the data from the studies included in our study and specific enough to distinguish between the theses (Ferrari, 1991). The included theses were coded as 1, 2,..., 144 to facilitate reading. There were formed 11 themes related to the thesis aims, 9 themes related to the results, and 11 themes related to the recommendations. Below are the codes or themes created for the aims, results and recommendations of the theses:

Regarding themes of the aims of the theses; *"To determine the frequency of dissociative experiences in the clinical population"*, *"To determine the frequency of dissociative experiences in the non-clinical population"*, *"To develop a measurement tool for dissociation/dissociative disorders validity and reliability"*, *"To investigate comorbidity in cases of dissociative disorders"*, *"To examine the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in the non-clinical population"*, The themes of *"Investigating the treatment of dissociative disorders"*, *"Investigating the etiology of dissociation/dissociative disorders"*, *"Examining the effect of traumatic experiences on dissociation in non-clinical population"*, *"Examining the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in clinical population"*, *"Determining the predictors of dissociation"* and *"Investigating dissociation from the perspective of art and/or religion"* were created.

Regarding the results of the theses; *"Childhood traumas are found intensively in cases of dissociative disorders."*, *"Childhood traumas increase the incidence of dissociative experiences/dissociative disorders."*, *"Dissociative experiences are experienced to a certain extent in the non-clinical population."*, *"Measurement tools for dissociation/dissociative disorders have been developed/validity and reliability have been conducted."*, *"There is a relationship between dissociation and traumatic experiences, family dynamics and other psychological characteristics."*, *"Treatment/intervention models specific to dissociative disorders are being developed and/or yielding results."*, *"Dissociation plays an active role in the development of psychiatric disorders/symptoms."*, *"Dissociative experiences/dissociative disorders are experienced to a certain extent in the clinical population."* and *"Other"* themes were created.

Regarding the recommendations of the theses; *"Not accessed/no recommendation."*, *"There is a need for more studies focused on dissociation/dissociative disorders and childhood traumas."*, *"Dissociative disorders need to be taken into consideration more in diagnostic evaluation."*, *"There is a need for more studies focused on psychotherapy/treatment of dissociative disorders."*, *"There is a need for more studies on the relationship between dissociative disorders and other psychiatric diagnoses."*, *"Cases of dissociative disorders should be handled in detail in terms of criminal and legal capacity."*, *"Comorbidities should be taken into account in*

cases of dissociative disorders.", *"There is a need for more cross-sectional and/or longitudinal studies on dissociative disorders."*, *"There is a need to focus on trauma and dissociation in the treatment of psychiatric disorders."* and *"There is a need for more studies and intervention programs to prevent traumatic experiences."* and *"Other"* themes were created.

Data analysis

The examined theses were subjected to quantitative and qualitative analysis based on the themes. According to the objectives of the associated themes, tables containing quantitative data were presented. The data are presented in this manner so that conclusions can be drawn about the entire thesis on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders. The tables included frequency statistics, and qualitative data were evaluated using thematic content analysis. Through thematic content analysis, the similarities and differences between the aims, results, and recommendations of the theses in our sample were revealed.

RESULTS

This section presents the results of a thematic content analysis of theses containing the keywords *"dissociation"* and/or *"dissociative disorders"* as key terms. It was determined that most of the theses on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders were conducted in 2020 (N: 14; 9.7%) and 2021 (N: 14; 9.7%), and after these years, most of them were conducted in 2018 (N: 13; 9.0%) and 2022 (N: 13; 9.0%). In addition, it was found that the most theses on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders were prepared as medical specialty theses (N: 80; 55.6%). Also, the majority of theses on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders were completed at Istanbul University (N: 20; 13.9%), Yuzuncu Yıl University (N: 13; 9.0%), Health Sciences University (N: 12; 8.3%), the Ministry of Health (N: 11; 7.6%), and Istanbul University-Cerrahpaşa (N: 10; 6.9%). Faculty of Medicine (N: 49; 34.0%), Institute of Social Sciences (N: 28; 19.4%), and Training and Research Hospital (N: 27; 18.8%) were the academic units where theses were respectively, the academic units where theses were completed.

As shown in Table 1, the majority of research on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders was conducted in the Department of Psychiatry/Mental Health (N: 67; 46.5%), the Department of Clinical Psychology (N: 27; 18.8%), the Department of Social Sciences (N: 14; 9.7%), and the Department of Child Psychiatry (N: 12; 8.3%), and 140 (97.2%) of the theses in our sample were original research.

Table 1: Distribution of the Science/Major Disciplines of Theses According to their Specialty (Original Research/Review)

		Thesis Feature			Total
		Original Research	Review		
Science/Division of Science	Department of Psychiatry/Mental Health	N	67	0	67
		%	46.5%	0.0%	46.5%
	Department of Child Psychiatry	N	12	0	12
		%	8.3%	0.0%	8.3%
	Department of Clinical Psychology	N	27	0	27
		%	18.8%	0.0%	18.8%
	Department of Social Sciences	N	14	0	14
		%	9.7%	0.0%	9.7%
	Department of Foreign Languages Education	N	0	1	1
		%	0.0%	0.7%	0.7%
	Department of Cinema Television	N	0	1	1
		%	0.0%	0.7%	0.7%
	Department of Ophthalmology	N	1	0	1
		%	0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
	Department of Applied Psychology	N	2	0	2
		%	1.4%	0.0%	1.4%
	Department of English Language and Literature	N	0	1	1
		%	0.0%	0.7%	0.7%
	Department of Clinical Neurosciences	N	1	0	1
		%	0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Department of Psychology	N	7	0	7	
	%	4.9%	0.0%	4.9%	
Department of Educational Sciences	N	3	0	3	
	%	2.1%	0.0%	2.1%	
Interdisciplinary Department of Social Psychiatry	N	1	0	1	
	%	0.7%	0.0%	0.7%	
Department of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation	N	1	0	1	
	%	0.7%	0.0%	0.7%	
Department of Public Administration	N	0	1	1	
	%	0.0%	0.7%	0.7%	
Department of Sociology	N	1	0	1	
	%	0.7%	0.0%	0.7%	
Department of Psychiatric Nursing	N	1	0	1	
	%	0.7%	0.0%	0.7%	
Department of Child and Adolescent Mental Health and Diseases	N	2	0	2	
	%	1.4%	0.0%	1.4%	
	Total	N	140	4	144
		%	97.2%	2.8%	100.0%

As shown in Table 2, the majority of theses on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders were conducted in the fields of psychiatry (N = 77; 53.5%) and psychology (N = 48; 33.3%), and quantitative methodology was used in 139 (96.5%) of the theses in our sample.

As shown in Table 3, it was determined that dissociation and/or dissociative disorders-oriented theses were primarily conducted for the following purposes of "Examining the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in non-clinical population" (N: 42; 29.2%), "Examining the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in clinical population" (N: 33; 22.9%) and "Determining the frequency of dissociative experiences in clinical population" (N: 26; 18.1%).

As can be seen in Table 4, in theses focused on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders, the most prevalent statements were

"There is a relationship between dissociation and traumatic experiences, family dynamics and other psychological characteristics" (N:38; 26.4%), "Dissociative experiences/dissociative disorders are experienced to a certain extent in the clinical population" (N:28; 19.4%) and "Childhood traumas increase the incidence of dissociative experiences/dissociative disorders" (N:24; 16.7%).

As can be seen in Table 5, in theses focused on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders, the most common statements were "There is a need for more cross-sectional and/or longitudinal studies on dissociative disorders" (N:23; %16.0%), "There is a need for more studies on the relationship between psychiatric diagnoses" (N:20; 13.9%) and "There is a need for more studies on dissociation/dissociative disorders and childhood traumas" (N:18; 12.5%).

Table 2: Distribution of the Subjects of the Theses According to Methodology (Quantitative/Qualitative)

Thesis Topic			Thesis Methodology		Total
			Quantitative	Qualitative	
Psychiatry	N		77	0	77
	%		53.5%	0.0%	53.5%
Child Health and Diseases	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Psychology	N		48	0	48
	%		33.3%	0.0%	33.3%
Forensic Sciences	N		7	0	7
	%		4.9%	0.0%	4.9%
English Language and Literature	N		0	1	1
	%		0.0%	0.7%	0.7%
Performing and Visual Arts	N		0	2	2
	%		0.0%	1.4%	1.4%
Eye Diseases	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Accidents	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Neurology	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Physiotherapy And Rehabilitation	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Religion	N		0	1	1
	%		0.0%	0.7%	0.7%
Political Science	N		0	1	1
	%		0.0%	0.7%	0.7%
Sociology	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Nursing	N		1	0	1
	%		0.7%	0.0%	0.7%
Total	N		139	5	144
	%		96.5%	3.5%	100.0%

Table 3: Distribution of Aims of Theses by Type (Medical Specialization/Master's/PhD)

Aims of Theses			Type of Thesis			Total
			Expertise in Medicine	Master's Degree	PhD	
Determining the frequency of dissociative experiences in a clinical population	N		23	3	0	26
	%		16.0%	2.1%	0.0%	18.1%
Determining the frequency of dissociative experiences in a non-clinical population	N		2	7	2	11
	%		1.4%	4.9%	1.4%	7.6%
Developing a measurement tool for dissociation/dissociative disorders validity and reliability	N		2	1	0	3
	%		1.4%	0.7%	0.0%	2.1%
Investigating comorbidities in dissociative disorder cases	N		4	0	0	4
	%		2.8%	0.0%	0.0%	2.8%
Examining the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in a non-clinical population	N		13	23	6	42
	%		9.0%	16.0%	4.2%	29.2%
Researching the treatment of dissociative disorders	N		3	0	0	3
	%		2.1%	0.0%	0.0%	2.1%
Investigating the etiology of dissociation/dissociative disorders	N		5	0	1	6
	%		3.5%	0.0%	0.7%	4.2%
Examining the impact of traumatic experiences on dissociation in a non-clinical population	N		2	3	0	5
	%		1.4%	2.1%	0.0%	3.5%
Examining the relationship between dissociation and psychological variables in a clinical population	N		26	7	0	33
	%		18.1%	4.9%	0.0%	22.9%
Identifying predictors of dissociation	N		0	4	1	5
	%		0.0%	2.8%	0.7%	3.5%
Exploring dissociation from the perspective of art and/or religion	N		0	6	0	6
	%		0.0%	4.2%	0.0%	4.2%
Total	N		80	54	10	144
	%		55.6%	37.5%	6.9%	100.0%

Table 4: Distribution of Results of Theses by Type (Expertise in Medicine/Master's/PhD)

		Type of Thesis			Total	
		Specialization in Medicine	Master's Degree	PhD		
Results of the Theses	Childhood traumas are found intensively in cases of dissociative disorders.	N	9	0	0	9
		%	6.3%	0.0%	0.0%	6.3%
	Childhood traumas increase the incidence of dissociative experiences/dissociative disorders.	N	11	13	0	24
		%	7.6%	9.0%	0.0%	16.7%
	The non-clinical population experiences dissociative experiences to a certain extent.	N	4	7	2	13
		%	2.8%	4.9%	1.4%	9.0%
	Measurement tools for dissociation/dissociative disorders have been developed validity and reliability have been conducted.	N	1	1	0	2
		%	0.7%	0.7%	0.0%	1.4%
	There is a relationship between dissociation and traumatic experiences, family dynamics and other psychological characteristics.	N	18	16	4	38
		%	12.5%	11.1%	2.8%	26.4%
	Treatment/intervention models specific to dissociative disorders are being developed and/or yielding results.	N	3	0	1	4
		%	2.1%	0.0%	0.7%	2.8%
	Dissociation plays an active role in the development of psychiatric disorders/symptoms.	N	9	8	3	20
		%	6.3%	5.6%	2.1%	13.9%
	Dissociative experiences/dissociative disorders are experienced to a certain extent in the clinical population.	N	24	4	0	28
		%	16.7%	2.8%	0.0%	19.4%
	Other	N	1	5	0	6
		%	0.7%	3.5%	0.0%	4.2%
Total	N	80	54	10	144	
	%	55.6%	37.5%	6.9%	100.0%	

Table 5. Distribution of Recommendations of Theses by Type (Expertise in Medicine/Master's/PhD)

		Type of Thesis			Total	
		Expertise in Medicine	Master's Degree	PhD		
Recommendations of Theses	Not accessed/no recommendation	N	11	6	0	17
		%	7.6%	4.2%	0.0%	11.8%
	There is a need for more studies focusing on dissociation/dissociative disorders and childhood traumas.	N	7	11	0	18
		%	4.9%	7.6%	0.0%	12.5%
	Dissociative disorders need more consideration in diagnostic assessment.	N	9	2	0	11
		%	6.3%	1.4%	0.0%	7.6%
	There is a need for more studies focusing on psychotherapy/treatment of dissociative disorders.	N	6	2	1	9
		%	4.2%	1.4%	0.7%	6.3%
	More studies on the relationship between dissociative disorders and other psychiatric diagnoses are needed.	N	9	7	4	20
		%	6.3%	4.9%	2.8%	13.9%
	Dissociative disorder cases should be handled in detail in terms of criminal and legal capacity.	N	1	4	2	7
		%	0.7%	2.8%	1.4%	4.9%
	Comorbidities should be considered in dissociative disorder cases.	N	7	3	1	11
		%	4.9%	2.1%	0.7%	7.6%
	There is a need for more cross-sectional and/or longitudinal studies on dissociative disorders.	N	14	9	0	23
		%	9.7%	6.3%	0.0%	16.0%
	Treatment of psychiatric illnesses should focus on trauma and dissociation.	N	9	1	0	10
		%	6.3%	0.7%	0.0%	6.9%
There is a need for more studies and intervention programs for the prevention of traumatic experiences.	N	7	5	2	14	
	%	4.9%	3.5%	1.4%	9.7%	
Other	N	0	4	0	4	
	%	0.0%	2.8%	0.0%	2.8%	
Total	N	80	54	10	144	
	%	55.6%	37.5%	6.9%	100.0%	

DISCUSSION

In this section, the findings of our study are discussed in detail in the context of the literature on dissociation and dissociative disorders. When the theses related to dissociation and dissociative disorders are examined, it is seen that the theses are mostly in the expertise in medicine program and in the original research type. The main function of theses is to enable a better understanding of the subject studied by reproducing it on scientific platforms. In this respect, doctoral theses in particular make a major contribution to the institutionalization of the field of study (Guntao & Laitko, 1991). These serve the academy not only to produce scientific knowledge and enrich the literature, but also as a "self-production system". In theses, the research methods, scientific thinking styles and the results that other disciplines have contributed to the literature facilitate both the structuring of the topics researched and the discussion of the results related to these topics (Salanda, 2011). In this perspective, theses also support the reproduction of knowledge and the acquisition of different new contents during reproduction. Our meta-synthesis study included 80 expertise in medicine, 54 master's and 10 doctoral theses published between 1995 and 2022. Since there is no meta-synthesis study on dissociation and/or dissociative disorders in the literature, our findings are discussed in the axis of meta-analysis studies on dissociation and dissociative disorders.

The recommendations "Comorbidities should be taken into account in cases of dissociative disorders.", "There is a need for more studies focused on psychotherapy/treatment of dissociative disorders." and "Trauma and dissociation should be focused on in the treatment of psychiatric disorders." (Table 5), which are frequently included in the theses within the scope of our study, focus on improving the treatment of dissociative disorders. Dissociative disorders are among the diagnostic groups with the longest average treatment duration (8-12 years on average) among non-psychotic psychiatric disorders (Brand et al., 2009). The study conducted by Langeland et al. (2020) on the economic burden of the treatment of dissociative disorder cases on societies also emphasizes that short-term psychotherapies specific to this psychiatric diagnosis group should be actively used by clinicians urgently, both in terms of the length of the average treatment period as stated in our recommendations and as stated by Brand et al (2009). In this direction, Ozturk's (2018/2021) "Trauma Based Alliance Model Therapy" and Ross and Halpern's (2009) "Trauma Model Therapy" are the main short-term therapies that can be used in the treatment of dissociative disorder cases. Apart from psychotherapies, pharmacotherapies are also one of the methods used in the treatment process of dissociative disorders. In a systematic review of studies conducted on the pharmacotherapy of dissociative disorders between 1967 and 2019, it was determined that dissociative experiences were experienced less in the group receiving pharmacotherapy (68.4%) compared to the control group (39.5%) (Sutar & Sahu, 2019).

The aim of "Developing a measurement tool for dissociation/dissociative disorders validity and reliability"

(Table 3) and the recommendation of "Dissociative disorders should be taken into consideration more in diagnostic evaluation" (Table 5) are among the prominent aims and recommendations of the theses we examined. A meta-analysis study on the diagnostic evaluation of dissociative disorders revealed that the SCID-D is a highly effective measurement tool used in the diagnostic evaluation of dissociative disorders. In the same study, it was emphasized that the SCID-D is a valid measurement tool that can be used to differentiate dissociative disorders from other psychiatric disorders (Mychailyszyn et al., 2021). Dissociative experiences at a level that can be diagnosed as dissociative disorder are also present to a certain extent in the non-clinical population. In this direction, the result obtained from our study, "Dissociative experiences are experienced to a certain extent in the non-clinical population." is one of the prominent findings in the theses we examined. In a meta-analysis study in which 31,915 university students were included in a total of 104 studies, 11.4% of the students were found to meet the diagnostic criteria for dissociative disorder (Kate et al., 2020), which supports the result that dissociative experiences are experienced to a certain extent in the non-clinical population in 13 (9.0%) of the theses we examined.

The results "There is a relationship between dissociation and traumatic experiences, family dynamics and other psychological characteristics." and "Dissociation plays an active role in the development of psychiatric disorders/symptoms." (Table 4) and the recommendations "More studies are needed on the relationship between dissociative disorders and other psychiatric diagnoses." and "There is a need to focus on trauma and dissociation in the treatment of psychiatric disorders" (Table 5) are closely related to both the connections of dissociative disorders and dissociation with other psychiatric disorders and symptoms and their importance in the treatment of these psychiatric disorders. A meta-analysis of the relationship between dissociation and symptoms of psychosis found a strong association between dissociation and positive psychotic symptoms. In the same study, it was emphasized that focusing on dissociative experiences during the treatment of psychotic symptoms may lead to positive results (Longden et al., 2020). The aim of "Determining the frequency of dissociative experiences in the clinical population" and the result "Dissociative experiences are experienced to a certain extent in the non-clinical population" are among the most frequently stated aims and results among the theses we addressed in our study. In another meta-analysis study, which included 19 psychiatric diagnoses and 15219 adults and included a total of 216 studies, dissociative experience levels were respectively; dissociative disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder, borderline personality disorder and conversion disorders are found from high to low (Lyssenko et al., 2018).

"There is a need for more studies focused on dissociation/dissociative disorders and childhood traumas." and "There is a need for more studies and intervention programs to prevent traumatic experiences." are among the most frequently mentioned recommendations in theses (Table 5). All traumatizing life events, especially clinical, complex and

cumulative childhood traumas cause dissociative reactions and the development of dissociative disorders when they cannot be processed (Kate et al., 2023; Ozturk, 2020a; 2020b). Lloyd deMause, the founder of psychohistory, states that the history of humanity in the "*Psychogenic Theory of History*" is based on childhood traumas and that individuals who experience similar traumatic experiences in this process are in psychoclasses characterized by similar psychological characteristics, and that childhood traumas should be eliminated in order for a healthy and developed psychoclass to emerge (deMause, 1997). In this direction, it is recommended to use the "*Natural and Guiding Parenting Style*" structured by Ozturk in the prevention of traumatic experiences, with this parenting style, parents will be able to raise their children in the healthiest way without physically disciplining and traumatizing them (Ozturk, 2022d). In addition, it is critical to develop long-term childhood trauma prevention strategies based on the "*dissoanalytic psychohistory*" structured by Ozturk (2023a/2023b) to prevent pathological dissociative experiences and dissociative disorders.

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